

disease developed in the continuous submergence treatment. Control treatments, in which the plants were not subjected to submergence, showed significantly highest disease with higher leaf infection and more sclerotia than all other treatments.

Prolonged submergence is not a favorable environment for rapid mycelia proliferation and infection in the host. ■

Effect of crop growth stage and N level on leaf blast monocyclic parameters on a new rice plant type

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We studied the effect of crop growth stage and applied N on leaf blast monocyclic parameters in two blast-susceptible cultivars, a new rice plant type line, IR64454-81-1-3-2, and with IR72 serving as the control (see table). Sporulation was converted to area under the sporulation curve (AUSC, in spores lesion⁻¹ d⁻¹) using the equation

$$AUSC = \sum_{i=1}^n [(X_{i+1} + X_i)/2] \cdot [t_{i+1} - t_i]$$

where X_i = number of spores produced at i th observation, T_i = time (d) between observations, and n = total number of observations.

The first greenhouse experiment used a split-split plot randomized complete block design with three replications. Three pregerminated seeds were directly sown in each plastic pot (500 cm³) of 0.5 kg soil, and the plants thinned to one plant at 7 d after sowing. Urea N (46-0-0) was applied in three equal splits. Inoculum (20 mL of *Pyricularia grisea* isolate PO6-6) at 150,000 spores mL⁻¹ was sprayed at a height of 1.5 m inside a 0.8 × 0.8 × 1.5-m chamber on 12 plants using an atomizer at 10 psi for 30 s. Plants were inside dew chambers for 24 h in a mist room for 5 d.

The second experiment used the same procedure, but 50 mL of inoculum was sprayed on six plants per sub-subplot inside a 3.5 × 3.5 × 1-m chamber placed in an air-conditioned room and leaves were sprayed with water hourly in daytime and covered with wet jute sacks and polyethylene sheets at night. At 12 h after inoculation, 1 cm leaf portions were cut from the top, middle, and bottom of three plants, fixed in 50% glycerin, and the number of spores counted. Leaf area was measured per plant using a Licor LI-3000 leaf area meter. Incubation period was determined by counting the lesions per plant daily starting from inoculation up to 7 d inside the mist room. Sporulation was assessed on five isolated lesions on the two upper leaves of three sample plants every morning up to 5 d of symptoms using small agar disks of known area. The number of spores produced per lesion was counted on three isolated sporulating lesions located on the two upper leaves of three sample plants at 3-d intervals starting 5 d after inoculation.

Crop growth stage affected leaf blast lesion area, severity, infection ratio, latent period, and AUSC (see table). Cultivar type affected all monocyclic parameters, except for the latent

period. Other authors have reported nonsignificant differences in latent period among cultivars with susceptible lesion types. Nitrogen level affected lesion area, infection ratio, and AUSC. Lesion area at maximum tillering stage was significantly higher than the lesion areas at early tillering and early booting stages. Leaf blast severity and infection ratio at early tillering stage was significantly higher than the leaf blast severity at early booting stage. Latent periods at early and maximum tillering stages were significantly lower than the latent period at early booting stage. The highest AUSC was observed at early tillering stage and decreased as crop growth stage progressed (see table). Leaf blast lesion area, severity, infection ratio, incubation period, and AUSC were higher on IR72 than on the new plant type (see table). Lesion area significantly increased as N level increased from 0 to 180 kg N ha⁻¹. The effect of N level on leaf blast severity was not significant. Infection ratios at 90 and 180 kg N ha⁻¹ were significantly higher than the infection ratio at 0 kg N ha⁻¹ but not between each other. A significantly higher AUSC was observed at 180 kg N ha⁻¹ than at 0 and 90 kg N ha⁻¹. ■

Effects of crop growth stage, cultivar, and N level on leaf blast monocyclic parameters.^a

Treatment	Lesion area ^b (cm ² plant ⁻¹)	Severity ^{b,d} (% plant ⁻¹)	Infection ratio ^b plant ⁻¹ /no. (no. lesions spores deposited plant ⁻¹)	Incubation period ^b (d)	Latent period ^b (d)	AUSC ^{c,e} (no. spores lesion ⁻¹ d ⁻¹)
Main plot (crop growth stage)						
Early tillering (15 DAS)	0.357 b	0.99 a	0.01248 a	6 a	6 a	2637 a
Maximum tillering (30 DAS)	1.036 a	0.27 ab	0.00392 ab	5 a	6 a	723 b
Early booting (45 DAS)	0.049 b	0.01 b	0.00022 b	6 a	7 b	109 c
Subplot (cultivar)						
IR72	0.772 a	0.54 a	0.00924 a	6 a	6 a	1440 a
New plant type	0.189 b	0.32 b	0.00184 b	5 b	6 a	873 b
Sub-subplot (N level)						
0 kg N ha ⁻¹	0.131 a	0.37 a	0.00368 a	5 a	6 a	718 a
90 kg N ha ⁻¹	0.442 b	0.44 a	0.00681 b	6 a	6 a	976 a
180 kg N ha ⁻¹	0.868 c	0.47 a	0.00612 b	6 a	6 a	1775 b

^aIn each factor within a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different by LSD at 5% level. ^bIncubation period = no. of days from inoculation until 50% of final no. of lesion is reached. Severity (%) = lesion area divided by the leaf area multiplied by 100. Latent period = no. of days from inoculation until 50% of the lesions start sporulating. Means of two trials with three replications. ^cMeans of three replications. ^dSeverity at 1 wk after inoculation. ^eAUSC = area under the sporulation curve.